

Template for a HamSCI Poster Using L^AT_EX

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This is a template for conference submissions to the HamSCI Workshop, and for HamSCI-related presentations at other conferences. By default, this template will produce a poster 48 inches by 36 inches in size. Beamer and PowerPoint templates can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18623265>.

Introduction

Welcome to beamer! You will want to switch your compiler to LuaTeX. Also, the compile time outs are getting prohibitive for beamer use in Overleaf if you don't have a subscription. I run as much locally as possible. If you are having trouble with LuaTeX, you may try removing the specialized fonts and dependencies.

Similarly, many of the colors have been adapted to live on the CWRU color scheme. You may choose to adapt the image banner or color theme to suit your preferences. If you use a beamer color scheme (such as beetle) you may want to adjust the footer color definitions if you want a colored bar at the bottom.

If you have some L^AT_EX experience, you can adjust almost everything in this poster. I've included some of my most-used features for newer users to use as a framework.

Formatting Text

Usual L^AT_EX formats work as expected. Color and style preferences can be controlled by the `.sty` files or manually.

1. this is a list
2. it lists things
 - this is a list
 - it lists things with bullets
 - ★ or other shapes

If you are new to L^AT_EX, a compelling reason to switch is the automatic text positioning on the page. You can control the color of text, emphasis, and other modifications using commands in the `.tex` file itself.

Blocks

There are a couple of types of blocks in beamer. You may want to keep things in blocks for easier formatting.

If you would like to edit how sections of text appear (e.g. outlines around blocks) like in a power point style poster, it will be easier to do that if everything is in a block. Make sure to include a title. Note that I have edited the title outlining for a lot of these blocks based on preference (and compact layout). Feel free to experiment.

I like to make this center column a bit thicker to fit figures. Feel free to change that by editing the column width; just leave some space for the margin between columns so things don't get too cramped.

Figures

There are a couple of ways to include figures. figure 1 shows how figures typically appear. figure 2 shows the more compact format I prefer. L^AT_EX has a built in reference system so that figure numbers are automatically updated for you, as long as you reference them by label and don't try to manually number. Similarly, there is support for linked citations (e.g. [1]) based on the `.bib` file.

Figure 1. This is a typical caption layout for L^AT_EX figures. Very lovely, not particularly compact.

Figure 2. (Left) Basic ionospheric signal propagation model for a Grape receiver. Image from Kristina Collins, KD8OXT (2021). This is an example of a more compact format, which looks more like a power point text box.

Technically, you can add figures without the figure environment as well, but it can be a touch unwieldy and it may be harder to get the figure right where you want it.

You can also include tables with reference labels. www.tablesgenerator.com is a good resource for converting tables from Excel into L^AT_EX-friendly format.

Table 1. Behold, a table.

Example Data	Equation Support	Images
3.14	π	HamSCI

We can reference this as table 1 anywhere in the document.

Alert

This is an alert box. It is another block type that can be freely adjusted.

Math Features

L^AT_EX is a wonderful format for typesetting math, chemical molecules, and even vector diagrams. There is support for inline math (using backslash-parenthesis ($a + b$) or $\$$ signs ($x = y$)). The compiler will be upset about any math signs ($=$, $+$, etc.) that are not contained in math mode. There is also support for a math display mode:

my favorite:
$$F(\omega) = \int_{\mathbb{R}} f(x)e^{-i\omega x} dx$$

Note that text in math mode (like math in text mode) should be marked as text for best results as math mode ignores spaces and uses a different font. For presentations, you may choose to use an equation command so that you can easily add reference labels for equations

$$e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0 \tag{1}$$

This can now be freely referenced with the `ref` command (e.g. equation 1) or with the `cref` command (e.g. equation (1)).

References

Any and all references in your `.bib` file will print out, so don't include a reference in the `.bib` file if you don't want it listed. L^AT_EX has a couple of built-in bibliography formats. I like `siam`, which I used here.

- [1] K. Collins, J. Gibbons, N. Frissell, A. Montare, D. Kazdan, D. Kalmbach, D. Swartz, R. Benedict, V. Romanek, R. Boedicker, W. Liles, W. Engelke, D. G. McGaw, J. Farmer, G. Mikitin, J. Hobart, G. Kavanagh, and S. Chakraborty, *Crowdsourced Doppler measurements of time standard stations demonstrating ionospheric variability*, *Earth System Science Data*, 15 (2023), pp. 1403–1418.